

doi:10.5281/zenodo.14840827

Factors Affecting The Implementation Of Nomadic Education Programme In Wamakko Local Government Area, Sokoto State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The nomadic education programme is designed to educate nomads through special effort because they have been lagging behind in this direction. However, some factors are impeding to the success of its proper implementations. This study examined factors influencing the implementation of nomadic education programme in Wamakko Local Government Area, Sokoto State, Nigeria. The objectives were to find out the effect of funding on provision of infrastructures and instructional facilities on the implementation of nomadic education programme; to examine the extent to which staffing affects the implementation of nomadic education programme and the impact of supervision on the implementation of nomadic education programme. A cross-sectional survey research design was used to gather detailed of information from respondents. Two research instruments were used to collect data for the study namely: Factors affecting the Implementation of Nomadic Education programme Questionnaire (FINEQ) and Interview Guide. Reliability of FINEQ was established with the use of test-retest reliability value of 0.83 and validity was determined through face and content validity with a CVI value of 0.90. One hundred and seventy (170) questionnaires were administered to respondents in the three (3) randomly selected primary schools in Wamakko LGA, Sokoto State. However, one hundred and sixty eight (168) questionnaires were returned. The major findings of this study are that there is a high influence of funding of provision of infrastructures and instructional facilities, a high influence of staffing and a high impact of teachers' supervision in nomadic primary schools on the implementation of nomadic education programme. Based on these findings, it is recommended that governments at all levels (local, state and federal) should give appropriate and enough funding on provision of infrastructure and instructional facilities; government should ensure adequate and qualified staffing, and teachers should be punctual and regular in the nomadic primary schools; and supervisors from Education Inspectorates of local, state and federal as well as parents and community leadership should have more time to visit the activities in these nomadic primary schools.

Keywords: nomadic education programme, instructional facilities, staffing

INTRODUCTION

Nomads' population has not been accurately enumerated in Sokoto State, Nigeria but according to National Commission for Nomadic Education (NCNE), 3.2 million out of about 4.6 million populations in Sokoto State, Nigeria are vastly living in the rural areas of which 1.5 million are Fulani nomads. In addition, the assessment shows the literacy rate among the nomadic population is extremely low for both girls and boys respectively to around 10 to 20 percent. Looking at this vast majority of the population living in rural areas as well as their life style hinders their access to education due to yet inflexible modes of education delivery. Thus, to find a solution for Wamakko increased access to flexible modes of education delivery that matches their lifestyle seems more challenging than it is thought.

There may be several other factors that prevent nomads' children from education and/or make education to nomadic children more challenging which are poverty (direct cost), child-labor (opportunity cost), but the core factor among the other is the Wamakko life style itself versus the national education system which is mainly designed to suit the sedentary communities more than Wamakko/mobile communities, this was due to the cultural homogeneity among tribes in Wamakko in local government (Mansory, 2009). Muhammad (2000) observed that Fulani herdsmen in Wamakko move seasonally from one place to another for grazing and herding, so they cannot stay for the whole schooling period (9 years) in one place. The low literacy rate in this community makes the issue more challenging when it comes to the teacher deployment, especially female. This problem is already been acknowledged by the education authorities in Sokoto State, Nigeria. The Nigerian education system is not yet inclusive of all children but a very promising beginning has been made. This research will therefore investigate the factors influencing the implementation of nomadic education of Wamakko Local Government Area of Sokoto state.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

The United Nations' 1984 Universal Declaration on Human Rights state that "everyone has the right to education". The government of Nigeria has committed itself to literacy enhancement of the Fulani. The National Policy on Education (2004) stresses that education is the birth right of every child, and education should be brought close to the environment of the child. The policy enjoins that whenever possible, arrangements will be made for such children to assist their parents in the morning and go to school in the evening. Special and adequate inducement will be provided to teachers in rural areas to make them stay in the job (NPE, 2004).

The nomadic education programme has a multifaceted schooling arrangement to suit the diverse transhuman habits of the Fulani. Different agencies are involved in the educational process. They work together to offer effective school system where the schools and the teachers move with the Fulani children.

The uncertainties of the movement of the Fulani make educational planning and student monitoring difficult. Unscheduled out-migration due to environmental failures or conflicts between the farmers and the pastoral Fulani disrupts school operations and classroom composition. Lack of appropriate use of funding forces the government to rely on volunteers or unqualified teachers. The poor salaries cannot attract the calibre of staff with the commitment to educational enrichment of the Fulani scarcity of chalks, books, pencils, and blackboards. Requests from schools for children to bring learning kits dampen the spirit of parents who think they have already made enough sacrifices by letting their children go to school rather than go on grazing (Sokoto Report, 2012).

In nomadic schools in Wamakko Local Government Area, about half of the pupils who have attended the school in the previous season have moved to another place. Many Fulani herdsmen ascribe erratic attendance and low enrolment in school to habitual movement and affirm that shifting settlements prevent the children from improving their literacy (Wamakko L.G.E.A., 2013). As a result of the movement, the teachers face the extra task of adjusting their teaching to fit the dynamics of the transient population. Some teachers cannot endure the rigorous movement of the Fulani. The initial zeal among unmarried teachers in nomadic schools fades soon after such teachers get married. Its against this background that this study focused on the factors affecting implementing nomadic education programme in Wamakko Local Government area of Sokoto state

Research Objective

3. Investigate the effect of supervision affect the implementation of nomadic education programme.

Research Question

- 1) How does supervision affect the implementation of nomadic education programme?

Research Hypotheses

- i. Supervision does not have significant effect on the implementation of nomadic education.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Supervision focuses upon the improvement of instruction. It is concerned with the continuous redefinition of goals, with the wider realization of the human dynamic for learning and cooperative efforts and with nurturing of a creative approach to the problems of teaching and learning. He also observes that supervision is consciously planned programme for the improvement consolidation of the instruction. It also means that the constant and continuous process of guidance is based on frequent visits which focus attention on one or more aspects of the school and its organization (Kajubi, 1989 and Kaweesi, 2002).

Kajubi (1989) confirmed that nomadic schools are not being inspected on regular basis and the inspectorate of education failed to act as a guide and a setter of standards for education institutions. This seriously affected the quality of education and educational services in general. This lack of supervision also presents great challenges to schools' infrastructure development and teacher working conditions. Also, the ineffectiveness of supervisors is attributed to inadequate facilitation. In addition, the heavy work schedule hampers their efficiency. Ironically, all the education reform commissions that were set up in Uganda from 1924-1964 like the helps-strokes commission of 1924, the de Bunsen commission of 1952 and the Castle commission of 1963 emphasized the need for effective supervision of schools and accordingly recommended the need to strengthen the inspectorate department. This is in recognition of supervision as a major component for monitoring, assessing and evaluating the education process.

Similarly, Kulbir (2000) cited by Tino (2010) observed that, nomadic schools' supervisions are highly unsatisfactory at the moment. It suffers from a large number of drawbacks among which are the mushrooming growths of these nomadic schools. While nomadic schools have multiplied tremendously, there is no proportional expansion in the supervisory system.

Kaweesi (2002) cited by Tino (2010) opined that due to many roles of supervisors and nomadic schools that exist today, there is irregularity of supervision system. Supervision takes place in a haphazard manner. The supervisor has so many schools under his charge that he cannot make a definite plan and evolve a time schedule. There is little arrangement for the follow-up of the supervision. The implementation suggestion and advice is not ensured. The improvement envisaged through supervision do not come about and every time supervision is carried out, the same suggestions and proposals are nowhere to sight. In the absence of follow-up, the impact of supervision remains unknown.

According to the Quality Assurance Task Force (2006), teachers need support to gain skills of maintaining and enhancing academic standards, pastoral care and social life of the pupils. Supervision measures high on the improvement of teaching and learning in schools. The purpose of supervision is to ensure that quality teaching and learning is equitably provided to all pupils and to facilitate the professional growth and effective performance of teachers (MOE&S, 2006). Teachers are the stable instruments of instruction with which supervisors work to improve teaching and learning. Supervision focuses on changing teacher behaviour to improve pupils learning process and products. Previously, supervising activities were conducted irregularly and in a skeletal form without using standardized instruments (Muhammad & Ardo, 2003). The emphasis then was mainly to collect data on the number of schools, number of teachers, and pupils' enrolment by gender, year of establishing the school and the funding patterns as well as the type of classroom structures available in the schools. The teaching-learning process was completely ignored. The data generated were inadequate and unreliable. To address these lapses, the Commission conducted series of workshops to develop suitable supervisory instruments. The outcome of these workshops was the development of Performance Indicators and Supervisory Instruments that enabled the Commission to collect reliable base-line data for planning and evaluation purposes.

Based on the finding from the study of Sanusi (2006), the developed supervisory instruments focused on: the Context, Inputs, Process and Outputs, of nomadic education. They are used to generate statistical data aimed at determining the status of some key variables. Examples of such variables include targets set in the National Policy on Education as explicated on the Guidelines for the Operation of Nomadic Education, or other official circulars in respect of number of schools, class size, gross enrolment ratio, teacher/pupil ratio, etc. As a result of increasing demands for education and the greater awareness of its importance, there was an indiscriminate establishment of schools by local authorities and the nomadic communities. The number of schools increased dramatically. This development created numerous administrative and management problems for the Commission. In order to streamline these nomadic schools and reduce them to a manageable number and thereby make the provision of education more effective, the Commission classified nomadic schools as either viable or non-viable based on certain criteria.

The criteria used in the classification of nomadic schools, according to Muhammad (2000) are:

- i. Adequate levels of pupils' enrolment and attendance;
- ii. Teacher availability and output;
- iii. Visible community participation in the development and management of schools;
- iv. Evidence of class work in pupils' notebooks;
- v. Record of steady progression in the classes;
- vi. Up-to-date teachers' lesson notes and scheme of work in the school;
- vii. Proper keeping of school records;
- viii. Availability of instructional materials and furniture for pupils.

In addition, the planning and conduct of the supervising exercise were enhanced, as a result of the following:

- i. Adequate planning in advance, at the beginning of each year on the nature and scope of the supervising exercise to be embarked upon;
- ii. Proper scheduling of activities and the provision of adequate funds;
- iii. early dissemination of information on schedule supervising activities to the schools, nomadic communities, local education authorities and the Federal Inspectorate Services; and
- iv. The provision of means of mobility such as 4-wheel drive vehicles for all supervising activities.

Modest changes have also been made in the manner schools are now supervised. For instance, the supervising officers from the Commission's headquarters along with those at the Zonal level jointly conduct the supervising of schools together with the Federal, State and Local Government officials. At the state level, the Federal Inspectorate Services based in the state, along with the State Coordinators of Nomadic Education Program participate in the supervision exercise.

At the Local government level, Local Education Authority (LEA) supervisors are involved, while at the Community level, the active community leaders as well as officials of Parent Teachers' Association (PTA) join the supervising team to take part in the exercise.

This is understandable considering the higher rate of increase in enrolment and number of schools, which necessitated the recruitment of more teachers many of whom, does not possess the minimum teaching qualification.

Another positive impact of the supervising exercise is that parents, local communities, local government and state officials are becoming increasingly aware of the important roles they are expected to play in the effective implementation of the program. The improved supervising strategies also engender skills development among the participants especially the parents and community leaders, who now use these skills to influence the improvement of their schools. The involvement of these external bodies in the supervising activities of the Commission appeared to have enriched the Commission's experiences and general understanding of the school system, particularly the rigours and complexities of supervising a

national educational program. Hence, the needs for examining the impact of supervision on the implementation of nomadic education programme.

2.5 Challenges of Implementing Nomadic Education Programme

The orthodox school curriculum is designed to suit the needs and experiences of the mainstream, permanently settled population. The curriculum derived from that background and its content draws from concepts, issues and illustrations that learners from there are familiar with and can relate to. Due consideration is not given to the peculiar circumstances and experiences of nomadic populations (Gidado, 2008).

According to Nafisatu and Abdu (2010), the following are the problems militating against the smooth operation of the NEP in Nigeria: constant migration of the nomads, the involvement of children in the productive systems, unsuitability of the formal school curriculum, physical isolation and restriction of the nomads from social interaction with the larger society, unfavourable land tenure system, underfunding of nomadic education and late release of approved funds, unwillingness of State and Local Governments to make budgetary allocations for Nomadic Education Program, indiscriminate transfers of the teachers by LGEAs from the Nomadic primary schools to conventional primary schools without replacements, Ibeneme (2011) find out that Learners from among the nomads have difficulty in understanding and relating. This makes learning content mostly incomprehensible. The use of the orthodox curriculum therefore constituted a major disincentive to their participation in education.

Another impediment to the nomads' full participation in education using the conventional approach is the use of the rigid formal school calendar and time schedules as stated by the (Talatu 2011). Learners are required to be in school at particular periods of the year and hours of the day. This rhythm has been carefully determined and established to suit the mainstream settled population and does not give adequate consideration to the seasonal migrations and work rhythms of nomadic populations.

Usman (2010) reported that One of Nigeria's drives towards the improvement of the quality of basic education is the introduction of a national policy on the use of mother tongue or the language of the immediate environment of the learner as the language of instruction in the first three levels of primary education. NEP started implementing this by adopting the use of Fulfulde, the predominant language among pastoral nomads as the medium of instruction in the first three levels of nomadic schools. The community language and culture should therefore be involved.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research design as explained by Kinner and Taylor (1981) is the basic plan, which guides the data collection and analysis phase of the research project. It is also the framework, which specifies the type of information to be collected, the sources of data and data collection procedure. In addition research design gives the detailed plan of what data to gather, from whom, how and when to collect data, and how to analyse the data obtained (Paulin, 2007). In order to achieve the objectives of the study, the researcher used a cross-sectional survey research design because the samples were drawn from different levels of respondents, as maintained by Creswell (2012). The researcher used students, teachers, headmasters, parents and nomadic community leaders as respondents.

The target population of this study covered all the three (3) nomadic primary schools in Wamakko local government area recognised by the Sokoto State Agency for Nomadic Education (SSANE), Ministry of Education, Sokoto as at the time of this study. The schools are: Fandirma, Diddiba and Runjin Biyo Nomadic Primary Schools. Table 3.1 shows the population of the entire people living in the area including students, teachers, parents and communities' leaders in Nomadic area of Wamakko Local Government Area. The total population as at the time of carrying out this research was twenty two thousand, five hundred and ninety one (22,591) people with two hundred and seventeen (217) students, twenty (20) teachers, one hundred and sixty four (164) parents and thirteen (13) communities' leaders.

Table 3.1:Nomadic Population in Wamakko Local Government Area, Sokoto State, Nigeria

S/ N	NOMADIC AREA	POPULATI ON	Communiti es leaders	Nomadic school	No of Teacher s	No. of Student s	No of Parent
1	Fandirma	7,578	4	School A	4	65	53
2	Diddiba	8,560	5	School B	13	83	64
3	Runjin Biyo	6,453	4	School C	3	69	47
Total		22,591	13		20	217	164

Source: Wamakko L.G.E.A (2024)

Sample and Sampling Technique

The sample size was calculated or determined using a simplified formula given by Krejcie and Morgan (1970).

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where n is the sample size, N is the population size and e = 5% (0.05) is the level of significance.

Purposive and simple random samplings were used to select key respondents (students, teachers, head teachers, parents and community leader) considering the fact that they are the subjects under investigation. Community leaders, parents and head teachers were selected using purposive sampling while students and teachers were selected using simple random sampling to allow each of them to have equal representation for the study.

Table 3.2: Population and Sample for the study

Category of the Respondents	Population size	Sample size	Sampling Technique
Head Teachers	3	3	Purposive sampling
Teachers	17	16	Simple random sampling
Students	217	170	Simple random sampling
Parent	164	20	Convenient sampling
Leaders	13	13	Purposive sampling
Total	414	222	

Source: Researcher's field survey (2014)

3.5 Method of Data Collection

This study employed the use of two research instruments namely; questionnaire and interview.

3.5.1 Questionnaire

The major instrument used for data collection in this study is questionnaire given in Appendix I. The researcher administered questionnaires to selected respondents (students, teachers and head teachers), conducted interview with some community leaders and parents. This is because questionnaire enables the respondents to freely express their views and opinions concerning the topic as long as they could read and write. Questionnaires were constructed such that all the information pertaining to the study obtained using close ended items.

The questionnaire used was named Factors affecting the Implementation of Nomadic Education programme Questionnaire (FINEQT). Items in this questionnaire were categorised into four sections A, B,C and D each section excluding section A, contains 10 four Likert-scale items questions. Section A was

the preliminary section which sought respondents' basic information, section B contains questionnaire items that dealt with funding on provision of infrastructure and instructional facilities on implementation of nomadic education programme, section C consists of items on the effects of staffing on nomadic education programme while section D is deals with the impacts of supervision on nomadic education programme. Funding on provision of infrastructure and instructional facilities on implementation of nomadic education programme,

The Factors affecting the Implementation of Nomadic Education programme Questionnaire (FINEQS) was also used for the students which has only two sections. Section A was the preliminary section which sought students' basic information. And section B contains dichotomous items that dealt with entirety of students' functions in nomadic education programme.

Based on Table 3.2, 170 students, 116 teachers and 3 head teachers were provided with questionnaires.

3.5.2 Focused group Interview

Interview enabled those respondents (parents and community leaders) that had difficulty in reading or writing to respond to the desired questions under study. These respondents could neither read nor write yet they have useful contributions to offer in this study. Hence, such respondents were interviewed. Focused group Interview was used for parent and community leaders. The interview guide on the objective had been made purposely to guide the data collection from the nomadic leaders and parents who could not understand the contents of the questionnaire. It contained open ended question that required respondents to express their personal views based on the situations available in their communities with regards to the objectives of the study. Focus group was organized for the parents to hear their responses.

3.6 Validity and Reliability of research instruments

3.6.1 Content validity

Content validity was used to determine the validity of the self-constructed Factors affecting the Implementation of Nomadic Education programme Questionnaire (FINEQ). The researcher distributed copies of the questionnaire to experts competent in the field Nomadic education programme for their contribution. The advantage of this validity type is to determine the extent to which the items of the construct represent the concept to be measured (Creswell, 2012). Content Validity Index (CVI) of the construct determined the validity of the both students and teachers questionnaires.

CVI for teachers/head-teachers questionnaire can be obtained by computing

$$CVI = \frac{\text{Number of items rated as relevant}}{\text{Total number of items in the scale}} = \frac{29}{32} = 0.90$$

While for students questionnaire $CVI = \frac{\text{Number of items rated as relevant}}{\text{Total number of items in the scale}} = \frac{16}{20} = 0.80$

The content validity index was 0.90 and 0.8 implying that the questionnaire was 90% and 80% valid for teachers and students questionnaire respectively.

3.6.2 Face validity

In addition to the content validity, face validity was also used to determine the validity of the research instrument. The purpose of face validity in research is to determine the appearance of a research instrument if it is appropriate for the concept of measure (Creswell, 2002). In determining the face validity, the instrument was submitted to the research supervisor and one senior academic staff in the Faculty of Education. The both recommended the suitability of the instrument.

3.6.3 Reliability of the Instrument

To determine the reliability of the instrument Factors affecting the Implementation of Nomadic Education programme Questionnaire (FINEQ), copies of the questionnaire were distributed to the Teachers, head-teachers and students and their responses were recorded in SPSS software and computed using Cronbach alpha. The purpose of Cronbach alpha is to test for internal consistency of an instrument (Cronbach, 1984). The tables below (table 3.3) indicate the total reliability of the instrument and the reliability of each construct. The reliability was found to be .842 for teachers' questionnaire and .821 for students questionnaire implying that the questionnaires were 84.2% and 82.1% reliable respectively. It was also

found that each construct of the instrument was reliable and no item needs to be deleted (*Cronbach's Alpha if item Deleted* <.842).

Table 3.2 Reliability Statistics

Instruments	Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
Teachers/Head-teachers FINEQ	.842	29
Students FINEQ	.821	16

DATA ANALYSIS

Research question three: What are the impacts of supervision on the implementation of nomadic education?

Table 4.16: Teachers' responses on the supervision and implementation of nomadic education programme

Table 4.19: Availability of nomadic education supervisors

Items for teachers (n = 17)	Count/proportion	SA	A	D	SD	Total
There are enough supervisors for nomadic education	Frequency	3	2	6	6	17
	Percent (%)	17.6	11.8	35.3	35.3	100.0

Source:Results of the analysis (2024)

According to the 12 (70.6%) of the teachers there were no available supervisors for nomadic education in Wamakko local government. while 5 (29.4%) of teachers admitted to have seen supervisors and that they were available for nomadic education programme. This therefore showed that nomadic education supervisors were not normally seen in every school of nomadic education of Wamakko local government area.

Table 4.20: Visitation of nomadic school by Supervisors

Items for teachers (n = 17)	Count/proportion	SA	A	D	SD	Total
Supervisors frequently visited the nomadic school	Frequency	1	3	6	7	17
	Percent(%)	5.9	17.6	35.3	41.2	100.0

Source:Results of the analysis (2024)

On thevisitation of nomadic school by nomadic Supervisors 13 (76.4%) of teachers disagreed they were being visited by supervisor while 4 (23.5%) of teachers admitted to were being visited by supervisors. This result therefore showed that the nomadic schools were not adequately visited or supervised by the supervisors of nomadic education in Wamakko local government area.

Table 4.21: The supervising regularity and punctuality of staff

Items for teachers (n = 17)	Count/proportion	SA	A	D	SD	Total
The supervisors ensures regularity and punctuality of staff	Frequency	2	3	7	5	17
	Percent (%)	11.8	17.6	41.2	29.4	100.0

Source: Results of the analysis (2024)

On the supervising regularity and punctuality of staff 12 (70.6%) of teachers disagreed the supervisors ensures their regularity and punctuality while 5 (29.4%) of teachers admitted that their regularity and punctuality to duty were being monitored by supervisors. This result therefore showed that the teachers 'regularity and punctuality were not adequately monitored by supervisors of nomadic education in Wamakko local government area.

Table 4:22 Supervision of on the curriculum implementation

Items for teachers (n = 17)	Count/proportion	SA	A	D	SD	Total
Teachers cannot effectively implement curriculum without supervision	Frequency	1	4	11	1	17
	Percent (%)	5.9	23.5	64.7	5.9	100.0

Source:Results of the analysis (2024)

On the curriculum implementation 12 (70.6%) of teachers disagreed that nomadic curriculum was being implemented accordingly while 5 (29.4%) of teachers confirmed to have implement nomadic curriculum accordingly. This result therefore showed that the teachers were not accordingly implementing the curriculum of nomadic education programme in Wamakko local government area.

Table 4.23: Supervision of nomadic schools by Nomadic community

Items for teachers (n = 17)	Count/proportion	SA	A	D	SD	Total
Nomadic community visit schools to supervise the activities	Frequency	4	0	10	3	17
	Percent (%)	23.5	0.0	58.8	17.6	100.0

Source: Results of the analysis (2024)

13 (76.4%) of teachers disagreed that their schools were being visited by nomadic communities to monitor their activities while 4 (23.5%) of teachers admitted to have been visited by nomadic communities in their schools. This result therefore showed that the nomadic community were not visiting and supervising the nomadic schools in their areas with a view to monitor their activities in Wamakko local government area.

Table 4.24: Supervision and Provision of free and compulsory for all nomads in this community

Items for teachers (n = 17)	Count/proportion	SA	A	D	SD	Total
Supervisor ensures that Nomadic educations is being Provided free and compulsory for all nomads in this community	Frequency	1	0	13	3	17
	Percent (%)	5.6	0.0	76.5	17.6	100.0

Source: Results of the analysis (2024)

Table 4.16 shows that majority (70.6%) of the teachers disagreed that there were enough supervisors for nomadic schools, 76.5% disagreed that supervisors frequently visited their schools, 70.5% disagreed that supervisors were motivating and guiding teachers to work better, 70.6% disagreed that supervisors ensured regularity and punctuality of staff, 64.7% disagreed that supervisor ensured commitment and disciplines, 82.3% agreed that supervision ensures strict adherence to rules and ethics, 70.6% disagreed that teachers cannot effectively implement curriculum without supervision, 76.4% disagreed that nomadic community leaders visit their schools to supervise the activities and 94.1% disagreed that supervisor ensures that nomadic educations is free and compulsory for all nomads in their community.

The majority of the responses indicated that supervision of activities was not sufficient and enough in nomadic schools

Table 4.25: Means of teachers’ views on the impacts supervision on implementation of nomadic education programme

Items for teachers (n=17)	Mean	Interpretation	Rank
There are enough supervisors for nomadic education	2.80	high influence	1
Supervisors frequently visit the nomadic schools	1.40	Low influence	8
Supervisors are motivating and guiding teachers to work better	1.38	Low influence	9
Supervisors ensure regularity and punctuality of staff	1.37	Low influence	10
Supervisors ensure commitment and disciplines	2.08	Moderate influence	5
Supervision ensures strict adherence to rules and ethics	2.77	High influence	2
Teachers cannot effectively implement curriculum without supervision	2.48	Moderate influence	3
Nomadic community leaders visit schools to supervise the activities	2.41	Moderate influence	7
Supervisors ensure that Nomadic educations is free and compulsory for all nomads in this community	2.46	Moderate influence	4
Average Mean	1.72	Low influence	

Source: Results of the analysis (2024)

Table 4.17 shows the means of teachers’ views on the impacts supervision on implementation of nomadic education programme. It is observed that among the measures, there are enough supervisors for nomadic education (mean of 2.80) is the most prominent. This is followed by supervision ensuring strict adherence to rules and ethics (mean of 2.77). The least measure of impact is supervisors ensuring regularity and punctuality of staff (mean of 1.37). Overall, there is a low impact of teachers’ supervision in nomadic primary schools on the implementation (mean of 3.18).

Table 4.26: Students’ responses for the impacts of supervision on the implementation of nomadic education programme

Parent visit to their children in nomadic school

Items for students (n = 168)	Count/proportion	YES	NO	Total
Does your parent visit your school?	Frequency	72	96	168
	Percentage (%)	42.9	57.1	100.0

Source: Results of the analysis (2024)

72 (42.9%) of students claimed that their parent pay them visit at schools to see their doings while 96 (57.1%) of students denied that their parent pay them visit while they are at school admitted. This result therefore showed that some parents were not monitoring the school activities of their children in nomadic school of Wamakko local government area.

Table 4.27: Supervision of Nomadic community leaders to schools

Items for students (n = 168)	Count/proportion	YES	NO	Total
Does the community leader always visit your school?	Frequency	96	72	168
	Percentage (%)	57.1	42.9	100.0

Source:Results of the analysis (2024)

OnSupervision of Nomadic community leaders to nomadic schools, 72 (42.9%) of students did not see their Nomadic community leaders pay them visit at schools to see their doings while 96 (57.1%) of students admitted to be seeing their Nomadic community leaders pay them visit while they are at school. This result therefore showed that some Nomadic community leaders were normally supervise and monitor the school activities of their communities in nomadic school of Wamakko local government area.

Table 4.28: Parent supervision to their children activities in nomadic schools

Items for students (n = 168)	Count/proportion	YES	NO	Total
Do your parents always look at your books and activities after school?	Frequency	5	163	168
	Percentage (%)	3.0	97.0	100.0

Source: Results of the analysis (2024)

Results presented in table 4.18 show that majority 57.1%of students representing said that their parent do not always visit them at school, 96.4% were of opinion that they had never received visitors in their schools, 97.6% disagreed that the community leader always visit their schools and 97.0% said that their parents do not always look at their books and activities after school.

Hypothesis Three: Supervision does not have significant effect on the implementation of nomadic education.

In order to ascertain the effect of supervision on the implementation of nomadic education programme in nomadic primary schools the above results were analysed using chi-square statistical tool. Table 4.19 below presents the result generated.

Hypothesis Three: Supervision does not have significant effect on the implementation of nomadic education.

Table 4.29: Chi-square test for the effect of supervision on implementation of nomadic education programme

Computed statistic	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Chi-Square	37.920	17	.002
Likelihood Ratio	43.140	17	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	32.832	17	.001
N of Valid Cases	168		

Source: Result of the analysis (2024)

Results presented in table 4.19 shows the χ^2 value for the effect of supervision on the implementation of nomadic education programme in nomadic primary schools as 37.920 and p-value = 0.002 < 0.05, for this the hypothesis which stated that supervision does not have significant effect on the implementation of nomadic education was rejected. This indicated that there is statistically significant effect of supervision on the implementation of nomadic education programme in nomadic primary schools in Wamakko LGA, Sokoto State, Nigeria.

Findings from the study indicated that there were no enough supervisors for nomadic schools; supervisors were not frequently visiting these schools, supervisors were not motivating and guiding teachers to work better. However, the study found out that supervisors used to ensure regularity and punctuality of staff. It was also found out that supervisor do not ensure commitment and disciplines, strict adherence to rules and ethics. The study further found out that teachers can effectively implement curriculum without supervision, nomadic community leaders do not always visit these nomadic schools to supervise the activities and that supervisors do not ensure that nomadic educations is free and compulsory for all nomads in these communities.

The finding of this study showed that among the factors, not having enough supervisors for nomadic education is the most prominent followed by supervision ensuring strict adherence to rules and ethics while the least measure of impact is supervisors ensuring regularity and punctuality of staff. Overall, there is a low impact of teachers' supervision in nomadic primary schools on the implementation.

Finding from the students also showed that their parent do not always visit them at school, they had never received visitors in their schools, the community leader do not always visit their schools and that their parents do not always look at their books and activities after school.

On this issue of supervision as it affect the implementation of nomadic education programme in the selected primary schools in Wamakko LGA in Sokoto state, community leaders interviewed and parents during the focus group affirmed the findings from both the teachers and students that:

“There are no enough supervisors in nomadic education. Supervisors were not frequently visiting the nomadic schools in their community and the community leadership was not also frequently supervising nomadic schools”

This therefore indicated insufficient and infective supervision for nomadic education in Wamakko local government.

CONCLUSION

From the findings of this study, it was concluded that there were no enough supervisors for nomadic schools, supervisors were not frequently visiting these schools, not motivating and guiding teachers to work better, do not ensure commitment and disciplines, strict adherence to rules and ethics. However, supervisors used to ensure regularity and punctuality of staff. The study further concluded that teachers can effectively implement curriculum without supervision, nomadic community leaders do not always visit these nomadic schools to supervise the activities and that supervisors do not ensure that nomadic educations is free and compulsory for all nomads in these communities.

Parents do not always visit their children in the schools and do not always look at their books and activities after school, students had never received visitors in their schools, and community leaders do not always visit these schools.

The conclusion of this study further indicated that among the factors affecting the implementation of nomadic education programme in respect of supervision, not having enough supervisors for nomadic education is the most prominent followed by supervision ensuring strict adherence to rules and ethics while the least factor is supervisors ensuring regularity and punctuality of staff. Overall, there is a low impact of teachers' supervision in nomadic primary schools on the implementation of nomadic education programme in Wamakko LGA, Sokoto state, Nigeria.

RECOMMENDATION

- 1 Supervisors from Education Inspectorates of local, state and federal as well as parents and community leadership should have more time to visit the activities in these nomadic primary schools

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This research work was sponsored by Tertiary Education Trust Fund (TETFUND) through the Institution Based Research grant to Shehu Shagari College of Education, Sokoto with reference number: TETF/DR&D/COE/SOKOTO/IBR/2024/VOL 11 BATCH 9: S/N0.21

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